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SOCIAL INSECURITY AND PRONENESS TO GET- RICH-QUICK- SYNDROME AMONG ADOLESCENTS IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA: COUNSELLING FOR NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Proneness to get-rich-quick syndrome is a strong attraction and preference to irrational and unabated desire to make money at all cost and to live in luxury. It is a breeding arena for social insecurity which is lack of confidence in one's ability to do well and it is a creation of a person's anxiety about what could happen in the future. This study therefore investigated relationship between Social Insecurity and Proneness to Get-Rich-Quick-Syndrome among adolescents in Lagos State: Counselling for National Development. The study adopted descriptive survey design with two research questions and three hypotheses. The sample consisted of 200 adolescents randomly selected from four secondary schools in Lagos State. A 30-item questionnaire titled "Social Insecurity and Proneness to Get- Rich-Quick-Syndrome Questionnaire (SIPGRQSQ)" was designed for data collection. Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.88. Data analysis was carried out using percentages, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, t-test and ANOVA. The first hypothesis was rejected while the second and third hypotheses were not rejected. Results showed that there exist a strong positive correlation between social insecurity and Proneness to Get- Rich-Quick-Syndrome among participants. Results also revealed that adolescents' Proneness to Get- Rich-Quick-Syndrome is neither gender, nor age-based. Therefore, there is need for effective counselling against attraction to Get-Rich-Quick-Syndrome which usually leads to social insecurity. Also, counsellors should assist adolescents in overcoming anxiety and worry about how to succeed in life through the use of appropriate counselling interventions. This will enhance our national development.

Keywords: Adolescents, National Development, Proneness to Get- Rich-Quick-Syndrome and Social Insecurity

Introduction

Across the world the world in general and in Africa in particular, attainment of tangible and sustainable national development is the quest of every leadership and institutions. National development is the capacity of any country to raise the standard of living of its residents. It can be achieved by providing individuals with basic livelihood and supplying them with employment (BYJU'S, 2023), as well as deployment of innovative approaches for mobilizing widespread and meaningful actions (Dreier, Nabarro, & Nelson, 2019). National

development refers to the expansion of institutions, improvement of a country as well as development of individuals (BYJU'S, 2023). It takes a holistic approach to the problems of unemployment, poverty, bad economy, insecurity as well as youth involvement in some anti-social behaviours such as cybercrimes, ritual killings, kidnapping, fraud and desire to make money at all cost which is known as "get-rich-quick-syndrome" (GRQS).

Ajide (2018), defines get-rich-quick-syndrome as an irrational, excessive and inordinate desire to acquire money and riches overnight. It is an unbridled quest for wealth due to desire for recognition, poverty, peer pressure, push from parents or religious houses as well as government's inability to provide jobs. Against this background, any vices such as internet fraud, rituals, armed robbery, kidnapping, prostitution among others thrive. It is a negative behaviour with several severe and dangerous consequences. This syndrome has capacity of attracting and drawing to itself unsuspecting and innocent adolescents. This will make them to be prone to the syndrome.

Enaikele, Adeleke & Adeoye (2022) stated that proneness to get-rich-quick syndrome is a strong liking, inclination, preference or attraction to irrational and unabated desire to make money at all cost and to live in luxury. It is a strong attraction and exposure to the ways and manners of those that are engaged in stupendous and extravagant lifestyle in the society. This is reasonably what attracts young people to those who engage in crime to be rich quickly by any means. Adolescents are easily drawn or prone to get-rich-quick syndrome because they detest hard work, they want to make quick money and generally want to live on the fast lane. Increasingly, youths are being dis-oriented by the get rich-quick syndrome on a daily basis (Salami, 2013).

In addition, Ukachukwu & Naetor (2020) stated that most of Nigerian adolescents are prone to get-rich-quick syndrome because they are low in self-confidence, agonized by poverty, threatened by lack amidst obvious plenty and suffocated by a deficiency of critical values and thus, become driven towards the welcoming arms of crime. Also, Ucha (2010) opine that inequality in wealth distribution, unemployment especially among youths and corruption especially among politicians and public office holders, has increased the rate of lack amidst the populace, thereby encouraging adolescents to be attracted to GRQS. Indeed, Nigeria is a rich country but majority of its inhabitants are poor because of inequality in wealth distribution (World Bank, 2020). The quest for wealth and luxury have led to an increase in crime and disregard for law and order in society with the kidnapping and killings of people for money rituals increasing on a daily basis Ijafiya (2022).

Cases of adolescents' unwholesome behaviour as a result of quest for wealth abound daily in the news. For example, Eno-Abasi, Odita and Timothy (2022) stated that in January 2022, some young boys aged between 14 and 18 years lured their girl friend to a hideout in Ogun State and beheaded her for ritual purposes. Social media is also full of pathetic stories and videos of activities of some young people that are engaged in get-rich-quick attitude. The rate at which young people crave for acquisition of money is unimaginable. This has led to a disgraceful trend in the society and has become a syndrome thereby affecting national development.

Dizik (2020) stated that the effect of GRQS could be more severe on young people when their expectation to get rich quickly cannot be met. When they are exposed to this syndrome, mental ill-health such as depression, anxiety, suicidal thoughts, addictions as well as

phobias could set in. In addition, Myers (2009) stated other consequences of get-rich-quick-syndrome are; low life-satisfaction, loneliness, anxiety, aggression, resentment and low academic performance. According to World Bank (2020), perceived poverty is one of the push factors for Proneness to get rich quick syndrome among adolescents in Nigeria. Others are; peer pressure, less reward for educational competitions, uncensored movies, value deficiency as well as fears and anxiety about what could happen in the future which is known as social insecurity.

Patterson (2023) defined social insecurity as lack of confidence in one's own ability to do well and succeed in social settings. Social insecurity is mostly a creation of the person's anxiety about what could happen in the future, rather than what has happened in the past. Someone with social insecurity might worry about appearing awkward, saying something hurtful or inappropriate or not being smart enough to contribute to the conversation or the society. According to Spicker (2001), it is a concept that is partly material and partly social; and that the first sense in social insecurity is the lack of basic security which is closely related to poverty. The second sense of insecurity is concerned with certain contingencies - things that may happen. Certain eventualities are unpredictable. These contingencies do not apply to everyone, but many if not most people are liable to them and this is the point at which adolescents are usually drawn or attracted to some anti-social behaviours.

The studies presented thus far provide evidence that there is a link between social insecurity and Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome among adolescents. Taken together, studies such as UCL IHE (2012) and Virtanen, Kawachi, Oksanen, et al. (2011), support the notion that lack is associated with an increased risk of depression while social insecurity is associated with sub-optimal mental health such as Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome. Strong social welfare systems coupled with good national development seem to offer protection against these risks. In addition, people with borderline personality often experience social insecurities pertaining to their own sense of identity. Such people may fear abandonment, doubt their own ability and depend excessively on others (Good Therapy, 2019). Social insecurity is a psychological orientation that has been found to be associated significantly with psychological distress (Fontana, et al. 1986). In other words, when people are extremely afraid of what could happen to them in the future, they get themselves involved in many negative activities, mostly Proneness to get-rich-quick-syndrome. Patterson (2023) submitted that someone with social insecurity might worry about appearing awkward, saying something hurtful or inappropriate or not being smart enough to contribute to the conversation or the society. All these establish the fact that consequences of Proneness to get-rich-quick-syndrome and that of social insecurity are almost the same. It also implies that when adolescents are dissuaded from Proneness to get-rich-quick-syndrome, then their level of their social insecurity will reduce.

Biplob, Umme, Aklima and Hossain (2020) observed that adolescents' life is very critical because their physical and mental adjustments are too difficult. Sometimes, they may fall down from their academic achievement because of social insecurity feeling, power, anger and lack of confidence which is threatening to their self-esteem, Sometimes, adolescents get attracted to drug abuse or anti-social activities like get rich quick syndrome. This study therefore seeks to examine if there is any relationship between social insecurity and Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome among adolescents in Lagos State, Nigeria and its implications for counselling for national development.

To aid the study, two research questions and three hypotheses were raised and answered at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Questions

1. What are the levels of social insecurity among adolescents in Lagos State?
2. What are the levels of adolescents’ Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome in Lagos State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between social insecurity and Proneness to get-rich-quick-syndrome among adolescents in Lagos State.
2. There is no significant difference between male and female adolescents’ Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome in Lagos State
3. There is no significant age difference in adolescents’ Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome in Lagos State.

Methodology

The study used the descriptive design to obtain relevant data on social insecurity and proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome among adolescents in Lagos State The sample for the study consisted of 200 adolescents randomly selected from four secondary schools in Lagos state. A 30-item questionnaire designed by the researchers titled “Social Insecurity and Proneness to Get- Rich-Quick-Syndrome Questionnaire (SIPGRQSQ)” which consisted of three sections: A, B & C was designed for data collection. Section A sought information on students’ demographic data, section B sought for students’ response on Social Insecurity while section C sought information on Proneness to Get-Rich-Quick- Syndrome. The instrument was validated by experts in the field of psychometrics. The reliability of this instrument was tested using the Cronbach’s Alpha reliability and its coefficient stood at 0.88. The questionnaire was administered on individual basis. Data obtained from the instrument was analyzed using percentages, Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, t-test as well as ANOVA to test the stated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research question 1: What are the levels of social insecurity among adolescents in Lagos State?

Table 1: Levels of Social Insecurity among adolescents in Lagos State

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Low	20	10.0	10.0
Average	74	37.0	47.0
High	106	53.0	100.0
Total	200	100.0	

Table 1 shows that the level of social insecurity is low among 20 adolescents which is 10 % of the total respondents; it is on the average among 74 adolescents which is 37% of the total respondents while the level of social insecurity is high among 106 adolescents which is 53 % of the total respondents This finding shows that the social insecurity level of more than half of the respondents is very high,

Research question 2: What are the levels of adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome in Lagos State?

Table 2: Levels of adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome in Lagos State

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Weak	28	14.0	14.0
	Mild	62	31.0	45.0
	Strong	110	55.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	

From Table 2, adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome is weak among 28 adolescents which is 14 % of the total respondents; their Proneness is mild among 62 adolescents which is 31% of the total respondents while adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome is strong among 110 adolescents which is 55 % of the total respondents This finding shows that adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome among more than half of the entire respondents is very strong.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between social insecurity and Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome among adolescents in Lagos State.

Table 3: Correlation between social insecurity and Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome among adolescents in Lagos State

		Social Insecurity	Proneness
Social Insecurity	Pearson Correlation	1	.920**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	200	200
Proneness	Pearson Correlation	.920**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From Table 3, it was observed that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) stood at 0.92 which means there is a strong positive correlation between the variables and the correlation p-value = 0.00. The correlation is therefore significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This then indicates that there is a significant relationship between social insecurity and Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome among adolescents in Lagos State

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between male and female adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome in Lagos State.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of mean and standard deviation of male and female adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Proneness	Male	87	36.55	9.490	1.017
	Female	113	37.39	12.625	1.188

Table 4 shows that the mean and standard deviation of male adolescents' Proneness to get-rich-quick-syndrome are mean = 36.55 & S D = 9.490 and that of female = 37.39 & S D = 12.625. This shows that there is no difference in their means.

Table 5: Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means							
	F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Diff.	Std. Error Diff.	95% Confidence Interval of the Diff.		
								Lower	Upper	
Proneness	Equal variances assumed	15.806	.000	-.517	198	.606	-.838	1.622	-4.036	2.361
	Equal variances not assumed			-.536	197.901	.593	-.838	1.564	-3.922	2.246

From table 5, the independent t-test conducted revealed that df =198, F= 15.806, and p =0.606. This result showed that there is no statistically significant difference between the variables. Hence, the null hypothesis was not rejected. In other words, there is no significant difference between male and female adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome in Lagos State. That is, adolescents Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome is not gender based. Hypothesis 3: There is no significant age difference in adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome in Lagos State.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics of mean and standard deviation of adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome based on age

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Min.	Max.
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
11-12 years	15	35.60	3.795	.980	33.50	37.70	32	45
13-14 years	87	35.29	13.733	1.472	32.36	38.21	17	59
15-16 years	98	38.23	9.815	.991	36.27	40.20	23	51
Total	200	36.76	11.471	.811	35.16	38.35	17	59

Table 6 shows that the mean and Standard deviation of 11-12 years old adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome are mean = 35.60 & S D = 3.795, those of 13-14 years are mean = 35.29 & S D = 13.733 while the mean and Standard deviation of 15-16 years old are mean = 38.23 & S D = 9.815. This shows that there is no difference in their means.

Table 7: ANOVA of age difference in adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome in Lagos State

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	421.977	2	210.988	1.613	.202
Within Groups	25765.018	197	130.787		
Total	26186.995	199			

Table 7 shows that $F_{(2, 197)} = 1.613$ and that $p > 0.05$. This result then reveals that there is no statistically significant difference between the variables. Hence, the null hypothesis was not rejected. In other words, there is no significant age difference in adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome in Lagos State. That is, adolescents can be prone to get-rich-quick-syndrome irrespective of their age.

Discussion

This study investigated social insecurity and Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome among adolescents in Lagos State Nigeria: counselling for national development. Findings from the study reveal that the social insecurity level of more than half of the respondents is very high and that the Proneness of these respondents to get- rich-quick-syndrome is very strong. This is in agreement with the position of Enaikele, Adeleke & Adeoye (2022) who stated that the general attraction of most adolescents in Nigeria to make money and accumulate wealth without necessarily working hard or sweating for it has increased astronomically. This is because the value which the present generation of youths in Nigeria seem to attach to a "get-rich-quick," mindset through cyber-crime and the use of human blood or body parts for money ritual is alarming.

The first hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between social insecurity and Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome among adolescents in Lagos State was rejected. In other words, there is positive and significant relationship between social insecurity and Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome among adolescents in Lagos State. This shows that the higher the level of social insecurity among adolescents, the stronger their Proneness to rich-quick-syndrome and vice versa. This finding agrees with the position of Biplob, Umme, Aklima and Hossain (2020) who opined that adolescents' life is very critical because of their physical and mental adjustments are too difficult. This may negatively influence their life; mood and they may become irritable and hopeless. Sometimes, they may fall down from their academic achievement because of social insecurity feeling, power, anger, stress and lack of confidence which is threatening to their self-esteem and make them disposed to some anti-social behaviour such as get- rich-quick-syndrome.

The second hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between male and female adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome in Lagos State was not rejected. In other words, there is no significant difference between male and female adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome in Lagos State. That is, adolescents' Proneness to get-rich-quick-syndrome is not gender based. This is in agreement with Myers (2009) who stated that one major consequence of get-rich-quick-syndrome is identity crisis which ultimately could result into lack of self-concept. This has always been correlated with low life-satisfaction, loneliness, anxiety, aggression, resentment and low academic performance. It

could be described as collection of beliefs about one-self that includes elements such as gender, sexuality, racial-identity and academic performance.

The third hypothesis which stated that there is no significant age difference in adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome in Lagos State was also not rejected. In other words, there is no significant age difference in adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome in Lagos State. That, is, adolescents can be prone to get-rich-quick-syndrome irrespective of their age. This position was corroborated by Ijafiya (2022) who opined that we are presently living in a time where you can see a young boy of about 18-25 years of age who has no meaningful source of income, live in very expensive and well-furnished apartment, put on expensive designer wears, and are not employee of any organization, nor do they have any visible means of income

Implications for Counselling for National Development

This study established that fact that there is a significant, strong and positive relationship between social insecurity and Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome among adolescents in Lagos State. The study equally revealed that the higher the level of social insecurity level among adolescents, the stronger their proneness and attraction of these young adolescents to get- rich-quick-syndrome and vice versa. To put succinctly, the study reveals that social insecurity is a push factor to alarming rate of adolescents' Proneness to get- rich-quick-syndrome. If this syndrome would be eliminated in order to promote national development, urgent steps must be taken to reduce influences of social insecurity in our society in general and among adolescents in particular.

Counselling is very key to achieving optimal national development and this could be achieved by providing entrepreneurial counselling to mitigate the challenges of rising unemployment situation in the country. Effective counselling would also in equipping the citizenry with worthwhile character, knowledge and skills needed for a prosperous life. It will also teach good values system which are panacea for a sustainable national development. Given the spate of brazen political violence, endemic insecurity and democratized corruption which have become common occurrences in Nigeria of today, counselling could be deployed as one the ways of promoting values orientation and national development.

In addition, there is also the need for effective counselling against attraction or Proneness to get-rich-quick-syndrome; provision of assistance to adolescents in overcoming anxiety and worry about how to succeed in life through the use of appropriate counselling interventions. Also, counsellors should encourage adults in the society to mentor these young adolescents intentionally; organize seminars and conferences on revival and re-orientation of moral values and virtues among adolescents and promote values of honesty, hard-work, uprightness, patriotism and nationalism.

Conclusion

The essence of this study is to find out if there is any link between social insecurity and Proneness to get-rich-quick-syndrome among adolescents and to possibly see ways of assisting adolescents in combating the menace of Proneness to get-rich-quick-syndrome in order to facilitate and promote national development. Counsellors, parents and other stakeholders must do all within their powers to give necessary attention to these young people and guide them towards national development. Parents should instill necessary moral discipline and ethics on their children while various organisations can get involved in

advocacy and sensitization of the general public on the danger inherent in social insecurity and Proneness to get- rich-quick syndrome.

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